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ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR THE ESTIMATION OF ELIGLUSTAT USING RP-HPLC METHOD IN BULK AND PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORM

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ABSTRACT

In RP-HPLC method, the conditions were optimized to obtain an adequate separation of eluted compounds. Initially, various mobile phase compositions were tried, to separate title ingredients. Mobile phase and flow rate selection was based on peak parameters (height, tailing, theoretical plates, capacity or symmetry factor), run time and resolution. The mobile phase containing mixture of 0.1% OPA (pH-3): Acetonitrile (30:70v/v) with a flow rate of 1.5 ml/min is quite robust. The optimum wavelength for detection was 260 nm at which better detector response for both the drugs was obtained. The retention time of Eliglustat was found to be 2.144 min. To ascertain its effectiveness, system suitability tests were carried out on freshly prepared stock solutions. The calibration was linear in concentration range of 84 to 420 µg/ml, with regression 0.9979. The low values of % R.S.D indicate the method is precise and accurate. The mean recoveries were found above 100.53 % for the drug. The Method was checked by doing validation according to the ICH guidelines. Hence the method is validated and it is used for the routine analysis of Eliglustat in its pharmaceutical dosage form by RP-HPLC.

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INTRODUCTION:

Eliglustat, marketed by Genzyme as CERDELGA, is a glucosylceramide synthase inhibitor indicated for the long-term treatment of Type 1 “Gaucher disease”. Patients selected for treatment with Eliglustat undergo an FDA approved genotype test to establish if they are CYP2D6 EM (extensive metabolizers), IM (intermediate metabolizers), or PM (poor metabolizers), as the results of this test dictate the dosage of Eliglustat recommended. Eliglustat was approved for use by the FDA in August 2014. Eliglustat is indicated for the long-term treatment of type 1 Gaucher disease in patients who are CYP2D6 extensive metabolizers (EMs), intermediate metabolizers (IMs), or poor metabolizers (PMs) in treatment-naïve and treatment-experienced adult patients.

Figure 1: Structure of Eliglustat

As there were no HPLC methods for the estimation of Eliglustat, the present work describes the development of a simple, precise, accurate, and reproducible HPLC method for the simultaneous estimation of Eliglustat in dosage form. The developed method was validated in accordance with ICH Guidelines [1&18] and successfully employed for the assay of Eliglustat dosage form.

Materials

Eliglustat was received under the brand name of CERDELGA, manufactured by Genzyme Corporation. Methanol, ortho phosphoric acid, potassium dihydrogen ortho phosphate, water, and trimethylamine were used which were of HPLC grade.

EXPERIMENTAL WORK:

Chromatographic conditions

The HPLC system (LC Waters, Milford, MA, USA) consisted of quaternary gradient system (650 Controller), in-line degasser (Waters, model AF), Ultraviolet detector (Water, 2487 model) and auto sampler (Waters, 2695 Alliance). Data was processed using Empower 2 software (Waters, Milford, MA, USA).

Isocratic elution of the mobile phase 0.1% Orthophosphoric acid (pH 3) and Acetonitrile in the ratio of 30:70 v/v with the flowrate of 1.5 ml/min. Separation was performed on a Waters C₁₈ (250 x 4.6 mm i.d, 5 μ particle size) analytical column and a pre-column to protect the analytical column from strongly bonded material. Integration of the detector output was performed using the Waters Empower software to determine the peak area. The contents of the mobile phase were filtered through a 0.45 μm membrane filter and degassed by sonication before use. Mobile phase was used as diluents.

The flow rate of the mobile phase was optimized to 1.5 ml/min which yields a column back pressure of 2500-2800 PS. The run time was set at 4 min and a column temperature was maintained at 25°C. The volume of injection was 20 μl, prior to injection of the analyte, the column was equilibrated for 30–40 min with the mobile phase. The eluents were detected at 260 nm. The developed method was validated in terms of specificity, linearity, accuracy, limit of detection (LOD), limit of quantification (LOQ), intra-day and inter-day precision and robustness for the assay of Eliglustat as per ICH guidelines.

Preparation of standard solutions

Accurately Weighed and taken 8.5 mg of Eliglustat into 10 ml of VF, to this add some volume of Mobile phase, dissolve it completely and make up solution up to the mark with mobile phase.
From above work take 3 ml to 10ml VF and make up with Diluent.

Preparation of sample solution:

Accurately weighed and taken an amount of Capsule powder equivalent to 8.5 mg of Eliglustat into 10 ml of VF, to this add some volume of Mobile phase, dissolve it completely and make up solution up to the mark with mobile phase.
From above work take 3 ml to 10ml VF and make up with Diluent.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Method Development:

Number of mobile phase and their different proportions were tried and finally was selected as 0.1% Orthophosphoric acid (pH 3) and Acetonitrile in the ratio of 30:70 v/v appropriate mobile phase which gave good resolution and acceptable system suitability parameters. The results of system suitability parameters were shown in table 2. The chromatogram of working standard solution is shown in Fig 3. The summary of Chromatographic conditions was given in table 1.

Table 1: Summary of Chromatographic conditions

S. No	Parameter	Description/Value
1.	Stationary Phase	Inertsil C ₁₈ Column (250mm x 4.6mm)5 μ m.
2	Mobile Phase	Acetonitrile: 0.1% OPA P ^H 3.0 (70:30 v/v)
3	Flow rate	1.5 ml/min
4	Detection Wavelength	260 nm
5	Detector	Ultraviolet detector
6	Injection	auto sampler -Waters, 2695 Alliance
7	RT	Eliglustat 2.144 Min
8	Injection volume	20 μ l
9	Column Temperature	Ambient (25° C)
10	Run time	4 mins
11	Diluent	Mobile Phase

Figure 2: Typical Chromatogram of Eliglustat**Table 2: System suitability parameters**

S. No	Parameter	Result
		Eliglustat
1	Retention Time	2.114 min
2	Tailing	1.41
3	Theoretical Plates (n)	3967.73
4	Resolution factor (R)	-----
5	Similarity Factor	1.05 (Limit: 0.98 – 1.2)

METHOD VALIDATION:**Accuracy**

Recovery assessment was obtained by using standard addition technique which was by adding known quantities of pure standards at three different levels in 50%, 100% and 150% to the pre analysed sample formulation. From the amount of drug found, amount of drug recovered and percentage recovery were calculated which sense to conformation that the proposed method was accurate. The results were tabulated in Table 3.

Table 3: Results of Accuracy of Eliglustat

%Concentration (at specification Level)	Area	Amount Added (mg)	Amount Found (mg)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	349165.3	4.2	4.27	101.69*	
100%	682988.7	8.4	8.35	99.46*	100.53**
150%	1034599.0	12.6	12.66	100.44*	

[*Mean % Recovery of 6 replicates; **Mean % Recovery of 3 replicates]

Precision

The intraday and interday precision of the proposed method was determined by analyzing mixed standard solution of Eliglustat at concentration 252 μ g/mL, 3 times on the same day and on 3 different days. The results shown in table 4 were reported in terms of relative standard deviation.

Table 4: Results of Precision (%Assay)

Sample No.	Eliglustat	
	Sample Area – 1	% Assay - 1
1	697409	101.51
2	690348	100.5
3	683414	99.47
4	682149	99.3
5	689131	100.3
6	679771	98.9
Average Assay	687037.0	100
STD	6522.9	0.95
% RSD	0.9	0.95

Linearity

As per ICH guidelines, calibration graphs were constructed by plotting peak area vs. concentration of Eliglustat and the regression equations were calculated. The calibration graphs were plotted over 5 different linear concentrations in the range of 84 µg/ml-420 µg/ml for Eliglustat. Aliquots (20 µl) of each solution were injected under the operating chromatographic condition described above [Number of replicates (n =5)]. The linearity graphs were shown in fig 4 & 5.

Figure 3: Linearity of Eliglustat**Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantitation (LOQ):**

The limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantitation (LOQ) of Eliglustat was determined by calculating the signal-to-noise(S/N) ratio of 3:1 and 10:1, respectively according to International Conference on Harmonization guidelines. LOD values for Eliglustat was found to be 2.98 and LOQ values for the same was found to be 10.03.

Assay of the tablet dosage form

The proposed validated method was successfully applied to determine Eliglustat in Pharmaceutical dosage form. The result obtained for Eliglustat was comparable with corresponding labeled amounts. The results were tabulated in table 4.

DEGRADATION STUDIES**Preparation of stock:**

Accurately weigh and transfer 8.4 mg of Eliglustat working standard into a 10 ml clean dry volumetric flask add about 7 mL of Diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent (Stock solution).

Hydrolytic degradation under acidic condition

Pipette 3 ml of Eliglustat of the above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask added about 3 ml of 0.1N Hcl and sonicated for 10minutes and kept it in darkness for 12 hours then refluxed under heat at 60 degrees in a heating mantle for 1 hour. Neutralized the sample solution using 0.1N NaOH and diluted up to the mark with diluents. The Final Sample was filtered through 0.44 micron Injection filters and injected into HPLC system.

Figure 4: Chromatogram showing Acid Degradation

Hydrolytic degradation under alkaline condition

Pipette 3 ml of Eliglustat of the above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask added about 3 ml of 0.1N NaOH and sonicated for 10 minutes and kept it in darkness for 12 hours then refluxed under heat at 60 degrees in a heating mantle for 1 hour. Neutralized the sample solution using 0.1N HCL and diluted up to the mark with diluents. The Final Sample was filtered through 0.44 micron Injection filters and injected into HPLC system.

Figure 5: Chromatogram showing Base Degradation

Peroxide Degradation

Pipette 3 ml of Eliglustat of the above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask added about 3ml of 3% Hydrogen Peroxide (H_2O_2) and sonicated for 10 minutes and kept in darkness for 12 hours and refluxed under heat at 60 degrees in a heating mantle for 1 hours. The Final Sample was filtered through 0.44 micron Injection filters and injected into HPLC system.

Figure 6: Chromatogram showing Peroxide Degradation

Thermal induced degradation

Pipette 3 ml of Eliglustat of the above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and kept in oven under heat at 105 degrees for 12 hours and diluted up to the mark with diluents. The Final Sample was filtered through 0.44 micron Injection filters and injected into HPLC system.

Figure 7: Chromatogram showing Thermal Degradation

Photo degradation

Pipette 3 ml of Eliglustat of the above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask added about and kept in darkness for 12 hours. The Final Sample was filtered through 0.44 micron Injection filters and injected into HPLC system.

Figure 8: Chromatogram showing Photo Degradation

Table 5: Degradation results for Eliglustat

Sample Name	Eliglustat	
	Area	% Degraded
Standard	685334.3	
Acid	639327	6.71
Base	625047	4.42
Peroxide	629327	8.17
Thermal	650258	5.12
Photo	626473	8.59

Significance of Forced degradation studies:

As per ICH guidelines, forced degradation studies are useful in:

1. Stability indicating methods.
2. Understanding into degradation pathways and degradation products of the drug substance.
3. Understanding the chemical behavior of the molecule.
4. Conducting studies on degradation mechanisms, etc.

CONCLUSION

The proposed method has advantage of simplicity and convenience for the separation and quantization of Eliglustat in the combination which can be used for the assay of their dosage form. Also, the low solvent consumption and short analytical run time lead to environmentally friendly chromatographic procedure. The method is accurate, precise, rapid and selective for simultaneous estimation of Eliglustat in Capsule dosage form. Hence it can be conveniently adopted for routine analysis. The future scope of the work is it is used for the bioequivalence study and by using force degradation impurities can be estimated by using LC-MS and NMR.

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ABBREVIATIONS

RP-HPLC	: Reverse Phase - High Performance/Pressure Liquid Chromatography
ICH	: International Conference of Harmonisation
IM	: Intermediate Metabolizers
PM	: Poor Metabolizers
EMs	: Extensive Metabolizers
LOD	: Limit of Detection
LOQ	: Limit of Quantification

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There is no conflict of interest.

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